

ON A CONJECTURE OF VICTOR GUO

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Abstract

In this paper we give a partial proof of the following conjecture of Victor Guo: If n and k are two positive integers with $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$, then

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

1. Introduction

The *binomial coefficient* $\binom{n}{k}$ is the number of ways of picking k unordered outcomes from n possibilities. The value of the binomial coefficient for nonnegative n and k is given explicitly by

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{(n-k)!k!}.$$

Since $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1}$, we have $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n\right) > 1$, where $\gcd(a, b)$ denotes the *greatest common divisor* of two integers a and b . If $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-1\right) > 1$, then, from $\gcd(n, n-1) = 1$ it follows that $\binom{n}{k}$ has at least two different prime factors. In general $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-1\right)$ is not always greater than one. For example, $\gcd\left(\binom{7}{3}, 6\right) = 1$. We obtain a similar conclusion for $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-2\right)$. The example $\gcd\left(\binom{14}{4}, 12\right) = 1$

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shows that $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-2\right)$ is not always greater than one. However, it seems that one of the claims $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-1\right) > 1$ and $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, n-2\right) > 1$ is always true. In this direction, in [2] Guo stated the following conjecture:

If n and k are two positive integers with $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$, then

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Based on a result from [1] and by applying elementary number theory, in this paper we prove that if $n-1$ is a prime power or $n-2$ is a prime power, double or triple of a prime power, then for any $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$ we have $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1$ (Theorems 1 and 3, respectively). Moreover if $2 \leq k < \frac{1+\sqrt{1+4(n-1)(1+\sqrt{n-1})}}{2}$, then the conjecture is true (Theorem 4). In addition, we derive two divisibility criteria which provide that $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1$ (Propositions 1 and 2).

2. Results

In [1] Gould and Schlesinger proved

$$\frac{n-i}{\gcd(n-i, k(k-1)\cdots(k-i))} \mid \binom{n}{k}$$

for every $0 \leq i \leq k-1$.

The results in this paper are based on the above divisibility property setting $i = 1$ and $i = 2$. For that purpose, in the following lemma we present the proofs of these cases.

Lemma 1. 1. Let $2 \leq k \leq n$. Then,

$$\frac{n-1}{\gcd(n-1, k(k-1))} \mid \binom{n}{k}.$$

2. Let $3 \leq k \leq n$. Then,

$$\frac{n-2}{\gcd(n-2, k(k-1)(k-2))} \mid \binom{n}{k}.$$

Proof. 1. Let $\gcd(n-1, k(k-1)) = d$. There exist integers x and y such that $(n-1)x + k(k-1)y = d$. It is enough to prove that $d\binom{n}{k}$ is divisible by $n-1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} d\binom{n}{k} &= ((n-1)x + k(k-1)y)\binom{n}{k} = (n-1)x\binom{n}{k} + k(k-1)y\frac{n}{k}\frac{n-1}{k-1}\binom{n-2}{k-2} \\ &= (n-1)\left(x\binom{n}{k} + ny\binom{n-2}{k-2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

2. Let $\gcd(n-2, k(k-1)(k-2)) = d$. Similarly like above, there exist integers x and y such that $(n-2)x + k(k-1)(k-2)y = d$. We need to show that $d\binom{n}{k}$ is divisible by $n-2$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} d\binom{n}{k} &= ((n-2)x + k(k-1)(k-2)y)\binom{n}{k} \\ &= (n-2)x\binom{n}{k} + k(k-1)(k-2)y\frac{n}{k}\frac{n-1}{k-1}\frac{n-2}{k-2}\binom{n-3}{k-3} \\ &= (n-2)\left(x\binom{n}{k} + n(n-1)y\binom{n-3}{k-3}\right). \end{aligned}$$

□

Now we are ready to give the first result in this paper.

Proposition 1. *Let $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$. If $k(k-1)$ is not divisible by $n-1$ or $k(k-1)(k-2)$ is not divisible by $n-2$, then*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. Let $\gcd(n-1, k(k-1)) = d < n-1$. From Lemma 1 we have $\frac{n-1}{d} | \binom{n}{k}$.

If n is an even number, then $\frac{n-2}{2}$ is a positive integer. Therefore $\frac{n-1}{d} | (n-1) \cdot \frac{n-2}{2} = \binom{n-1}{2}$. Since $\frac{n-1}{d} | \binom{n}{k}$ and $\frac{n-1}{d} | \binom{n-1}{2}$ we have $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) \geq \frac{n-1}{d} > 1$.

If n is an odd number, then $\gcd(n-1, k(k-1)) = d = 2d'$. Thus, $\frac{n-1}{d} | \frac{n-1}{2}$, that is, $\frac{n-1}{d} | \binom{n-1}{2}$. Again we obtain $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) \geq \frac{n-1}{d} > 1$.

Following the same reasoning as above we easily prove that if $\gcd(n-2, k(k-1)(k-2)) = d < n-2$, then $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-2}{2}\right) \geq \frac{n-2}{d} > 1$. □

From now on we assume that $k(k-1)$ is divisible by $n-1$ and $k(k-1)(k-2)$ is divisible by $n-2$. This assumption leads to the following result.

Theorem 1. *If $n-1$ or $n-2$ is a prime power, then for any k such that $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$,*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. Let p be a prime number and let $n-1 = p^e$ or $n-2 = p^e$. Since $n-1 | k(k-1)$ and $n-2 | k(k-1)(k-2)$ we obtain $p^e | k(k-1)$ or $p^e | k(k-1)(k-2)$.

If $n-1 = p^e$, then from $\gcd(k, k-1) = 1$ we get $p^e | k$ or $p^e | k-1$. This is in contradiction to $p^e = n-1 \geq 2k-1$.

If $n-2 = p^e$, then we consider two cases. If $p \geq 3$, then from $p^e | k(k-1)(k-2)$ and $\gcd(k, k-1, k-2) = 1$, $\gcd(k, k-2) \leq 2$ we have $p^e | k$ or $p^e | k-1$ or $p^e | k-2$. As above, these three divisibilities are not possible. If $p = 2$, then $n-2 = 2^e$ and $2^e | k(k-1)(k-2)$. Since $k \leq \frac{n}{2}$ we get $k \leq 2^{e-1} + 1$.

If k is an odd number, then $2^e|k-1$; this divisibility is not possible since $k-1 \leq 2^{e-1}$.

If k is an even number, then $2^{e-1}|k$ or $2^{e-1}|k-2$. If $k = 2^{e-1}$, then from Lemma 1 we have

$$\frac{2^e + 1}{\gcd(2^e + 1, 2^{e-1}(2^{e-1} - 1))} \mid \binom{2^e + 2}{2^{e-1}}.$$

Since $\gcd(2^e + 1, 2^{e-1}(2^{e-1} - 1)) \in \{1, 3\}$ we get $2^e + 1 \mid \binom{2^e+2}{2^{e-1}}$ or $\frac{2^e+1}{3} \mid \binom{2^e+2}{2^{e-1}}$.

On the other hand

$$\binom{n-1}{2} = \binom{2^e+1}{2} = \frac{(2^e+1)2^e}{2} = (2^e+1)2^{e-1}.$$

Thus we obtain

$$\gcd\left(\binom{2^e+2}{2^{e-1}}, \binom{2^e+1}{2}\right) \geq \frac{2^e+1}{3} > 1.$$

If $k \leq 2^{e-1}$, then 2^{e-1} does not divide k and $k-2$.

□

Proposition 2. *Let k, n be integers such that $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$ and $\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) = 1$. Then there exist positive integers a and c such that*

$$k(k-1) = a(n-1)$$

$$a(k-2) = c(n-2).$$

Moreover

$$\frac{a^2}{c} - 1 < k < \frac{a^2}{c} - \frac{1}{2}$$

and

$$n-2 \mid a(a-2).$$

Proof. Since $k = 2$ does not satisfy the conditions we assume $k \geq 3$. Moreover, let us suppose that $\gcd(n-1, k(k-1)) = n-1$ and $\gcd(n-2, k(k-1)(k-2)) = n-2$. Hence, there exist positive integers a and b such that $k(k-1) = a(n-1)$ and $k(k-1)(k-2) = b(n-2)$. It is easy to see that $n-1$ divides $b(n-2)$. Since $\gcd(n-1, n-2) = 1$, we obtain that b is a multiple of $n-1$, that is, there exists a positive integer c such that $b = c(n-1)$. Thus we obtain the following two equations

$$k(k-1) = a(n-1) \tag{1}$$

$$k(k-1)(k-2) = c(n-1)(n-2). \tag{2}$$

Replacing (1) in (2) and using $n-1 = \frac{k(k-1)}{a}$ we obtain $a(k-2) = c\left(\frac{k(k-1)}{a} - 1\right)$, that is, we obtain the following quadratic equation in k

$$ck^2 - k(a^2 + c) + 2a^2 - ac = 0. \tag{3}$$

Solving (3) we get

$$k_{1,2} = \frac{a^2 + c \pm \sqrt{a^4 - 6a^2c + 4ac^2 + c^2}}{2c}. \tag{4}$$

Since k is a natural number, the discriminant of (3) is a perfect square. There exists a positive integer t such that $a^4 - 6a^2c + 4ac^2 + c^2 = t^2$. We will show that

$$0 < a^2 - 3c < t < a^2 - 2c. \tag{5}$$

Dividing (2) by (1) we get $\frac{c}{a} = \frac{k-2}{n-2} < \frac{k}{n} \leq \frac{1}{2}$. Hence

$$t^2 < (a^2 - 2c)^2 \Leftrightarrow 0 < ac(2a - 4c) + 3c^2 \Leftrightarrow 0 < ac(2a - 4c) \Leftrightarrow 2c < a.$$

From $a > 2c \geq 2$ and $t^2 = (a^2 - 3c)^2 + 4(a - 2)c^2$ we derive the lower bound.

By (4) we obtain that k is of the form $\frac{a^2+c+t}{2c}$. If $k = \frac{a^2+c-t}{2c}$, then we have

$$\frac{3}{2} = \frac{a^2 + c - a^2 + 2c}{2c} < k < \frac{a^2 + c - a^2 + 3c}{2c} = 2.$$

Therefore

$$k = \frac{a^2 + c + t}{2c} \tag{6}$$

and

$$\frac{a^2}{c} - 1 = \frac{a^2 + c + a^2 - 3c}{2c} < k < \frac{a^2 + c + a^2 - 2c}{2c} = \frac{a^2}{c} - \frac{1}{2}.$$

Substituting $c = \frac{a^2(k-2)}{k^2-k-a}$ in (6) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} t = 2ck - a^2 - c &= \frac{a^2(k^2 - 4k + a + 2)}{k^2 - k - a} = \frac{a^2(k^2 - 4k + a + 2)}{k^2 - k - a} \frac{k - 2}{k - 2} \\ &= c \frac{k^2 - 4k + a + 2}{k - 2} = c(k - 2) + \frac{c(a - 2)}{k - 2}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $k - 2|c(a - 2)$, that is, $a(k - 2)|ca(a - 2)$. From $a(k - 2) = c(n - 2)$ we get

$$n - 2|a(a - 2).$$

□

The next result follows directly from Proposition 2.

Theorem 2. *Let $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$. If $\frac{k^2(k-1)^2 - 2k(k-1)(n-1)}{(n-2)(n-1)^2}$ is not an integer, then*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proposition 3. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime number such that $p^e | n - 2$. Then for any $k \in \left[2, \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4p^e(n-1)}}{2}\right)$ we have*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. According to Proposition 2 it suffices to prove that $n - 2$ does not divide $a(a - 2)$, where $a = \frac{k(k-1)}{n-1}$.

Let $n - 2 | a(a - 2)$. Hence $p^e | a(a - 2)$. Since $p \geq 3$ and $\gcd(a, a - 2) \leq 2$, we have $p^e | a$ or $p^e | a - 2$. We will show that this is not possible by proving $p^e > a = \frac{k(k-1)}{n-1}$. We have

$$p^e > \frac{k(k-1)}{n-1} \Leftrightarrow k^2 - k - p^e(n-1) < 0 \Leftrightarrow k \in \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{1 + 4p^e(n-1)}}{2}, \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4p^e(n-1)}}{2}\right).$$

□

The case $p = 2$ is considered in the following proposition.

Proposition 4. *Let $2^e | n - 2$. Then for any $k \in \left[2, \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 2^{e+1}(n-1)}}{2}\right)$ we have*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. Similarly as in the previous proposition we assume $n - 2 | a(a - 2)$. Therefore $2^e | a(a - 2)$. Clearly a is an even number and $\gcd(a, a - 2) = 2$. Thus $2^{e-1} | a$ or $2^{e-1} | a - 2$. On the other hand, from $k < \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 2^{e+1}(n-1)}}{2}$ we obtain $2^{e-1} > \frac{k(k-1)}{n-1} = a$. This conclusion is in contradiction to $2^{e-1} | a$ or $2^{e-1} | a - 2$. □

Theorem 3. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime number. If $n = 2p^e + 2$ or $n = 3p^e + 2$ and $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}$, then*

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. The proof relies on Proposition 3 by showing $\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4p^e(n-1)}}{2} > \frac{n}{2}$. Since $p^e \geq \frac{n-2}{3}$ and since $\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4p^e(n-1)}}{2} > \frac{n}{2}$ is equivalent to $p^e > \frac{n-1}{4} - \frac{1}{4(n-1)}$, it is enough to prove

$$\frac{n-2}{3} > \frac{n-1}{4} - \frac{1}{4(n-1)}. \tag{7}$$

From the conditions we can take $n > 5$. This assumption is equivalent to $\frac{n-2}{3} > \frac{n-1}{4}$, which leads to the inequality (7). □

Theorem 4. If $2 \leq k < \frac{1+\sqrt{1+4(n-1)(1+\sqrt{n-1})}}{2}$, then

$$\gcd\left(\binom{n}{k}, \binom{n-1}{2}\right) > 1.$$

Proof. If $k^2(k-1)^2 - 2k(k-1)(n-1) < (n-2)(n-1)^2$, then $\frac{k^2(k-1)^2 - 2k(k-1)(n-1)}{(n-2)(n-1)^2}$ is not an integer, which leads to the positive answer of the conjecture. Setting $t = k(k-1)$ and solving the quadratic inequality $t^2 - 2t(n-1) - (n-2)(n-1)^2 < 0$ we obtain $t \in ((n-1) - (n-1)\sqrt{n-1}, (n-1) + (n-1)\sqrt{n-1})$. Since $t = k(k-1) > 0$ we have $k(k-1) < (n-1)(1 + \sqrt{n-1})$. Solving the inequality $k^2 - k - (n-1)(1 + \sqrt{n-1}) < 0$ we obtain $k < \frac{1+\sqrt{1+4(n-1)(1+\sqrt{n-1})}}{2}$. \square

References

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